

A Practical Implementation of Twin Types

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Abstract

In a previous publication [8], an approach to higher-order unification in a dependently-typed setting is described and benchmarked on a specific case study by means of a prototype. In this follow-up we evaluate the practicality of our approach by implementing it in an existing proof assistant (Agda), and benchmarking it on a selection of projects, including the Agda standard library. This solves some bugs in the current Agda implementation, with no large effect on performance and a limited amount of changes to the code of Agda.

When defining functions in a dependently-typed proof assistant, users may mark some function arguments as implicit, either for readability or for code writing speed. The type checker needs to infer these arguments when the function is used.

Inference of implicit arguments in proof assistants such as Coq, Lean, Idris or Agda is done by replacing the implicit arguments with placeholders of an appropriate type (i.e. metavariables), and applying the typing rules to produce a series of unification constraints. A unification constraint consists of at least a pair of terms t and u in a typing context Γ ($\Gamma \vdash t \approx u$). A constraint is solved by assigning terms to the placeholders so that both sides of the constraint become equal ($\Gamma \vdash t \equiv u$). A constraint of the form $\Gamma \vdash \alpha \approx t$ can be solved by assigning $\alpha := t$. The creation of ill-typed terms can be avoided by either check that t has the right type before assigning it to α , which could incur a performance penalty; or by ensuring that both sides of every constraint have the same context and type, which is the preferred approach.

Binder problem A common problem in dependently-typed unification arises when unifying binders. For instance, a constraint of the form $\Gamma \vdash (x : A) \rightarrow B \approx (x : A') \rightarrow B'$ may be solved by separately unifying the domains and the codomains. However, the types B and B' live in different contexts ($\Gamma, x : A \vdash B$ **type** and $\Gamma, x : A' \vdash B'$ **type**). It is not self-evident what the type of x should be in $\Gamma, x : ? \vdash B \approx B'$ **type**.

Spine problem Consider an irreducible constant $c : (x : A) \rightarrow (y : B) \rightarrow C$ (e.g. a data constructor). The spine problem arises for instance when solving $\Gamma \vdash ctu \approx ct'u'$, which is done by unifying $\Gamma \vdash t \approx t' : A$ and $\Gamma \vdash u \approx u'$. Until t and t' can be unified, u and u' may lack a common type. This may threaten the soundness of ensuing metavariable instantiations.

Coq In our tests, Coq [17] will refuse to unify the domain before the codomain, thus avoiding the binder problem. Ziliani and Sozeau [18] argue that in the context of Coq, constraint postponement is not crucial, and may even worsen the performance of the algorithm and make it harder to debug. The Lean proof assistant behaves similarly to Coq. The spine problem in Coq is also avoided by solving the constraints in a suitable order.

Agda In Agda constraints are well-typed modulo other constraints being solved. The presence of ill-typed terms may however cause issues, as described by Norell and Coquand [12, 14]. To mitigate them, the type of the variable is replaced by a blocked constant. That is, $\Gamma, x : p \vdash B \approx B'$, where p reduces to A ($p \rightsquigarrow A$) when $\Gamma \vdash A \equiv A'$. The resulting terms are still

	kLOC	CPU (s)		Memory (MB)	
		Ours	Baseline	Ours	Baseline
Prelude	12.6	110±1.2 (+5.1...+1.8%)	106±1.2	573±15 (+6.0...-1.8%)	562±17
Std-Lib	93.6	531±7.8 (+0.7...-2.8%)	537±5.3	1690±12 (-3.7...-5.3%)	1770± 8
HoTT	29.7	223±2.2 (+5.9...+3.1%)	214±2.1	1910±36 (-2.6...-7.4%)	2010±35

Table 1: Performance when type-checking some Agda projects, namely the Agda prelude [15], the Agda standard library [4], and “Introduction to HoTT” [16]. The size in thousands of lines of code is given, followed by estimations of the median time and memory used by our implementation [9] and the percentual variation with respect to the version of Agda it is based on [2] ($n = 40$, 95% CI). We observe no large differences between the two implementations.

potentially not well-typed, which in some known cases causes the type-checker to crash [10]. Agda mitigates the spine problem in a similar way, but it is not a complete solution [3, 13].

Idris 2 Idris 2 is a programming language focused on type-driven development. The binder problem is solved by taking $x : A$, and replacing all occurrences of x in B' by a blocked constant; i.e. $\Gamma, x : A \vdash B \approx B'[p/x]$ **type**, where $p \rightsquigarrow x$ when $\Gamma \vdash A \equiv A'$. As opposed to replacing the type of the variable, as done in Agda, blocking the variable produces well-typed terms. This straightforward approach was however not flexible enough to support some existing Agda code [1], and does not address the spine problem.

An approach based on twin types Gundry and McBride [6, 5] propose a solution based on assigning two types to each variable, and annotating each occurrence of the variable in a term to distinguish which type applies. A streamlined variant of their approach without the annotations [8, 7] has been implemented in an existing prototype [11] and used to type-check some specific examples. It remained to show that the approach scales to a larger proof assistant.

Evaluation results We have implemented the method we described in previous publications [8, 7] (with suitable extensions) into the Agda type checker [2]. The implementation took 18 weeks of work at 25 hours per week. Less than 2700 lines of code (6.7% of the codebase) were added or modified, partly thanks to keeping the term syntax intact. Implementing our approach in Agda fixes some long-standing bugs either outright [10] or without resorting to workarounds [3, 13]. We have tested our implementation [9] on three large Agda projects, yielding comparable CPU and memory usage (Table 1). Note that hash consing, which was used for performance in a previous prototype [8, 7], was not required here.

Limitations This approach does not preserve all the power of the existing Agda implementation. For instance, four instances of implicit arguments in the standard library which were previously inferred by Agda had to be given explicitly. For other projects with different coding styles, the figure may be larger. Support for Agda’s cubical type theory features is pending.

Conclusion Despite the limitations, heterogeneous higher-order unification is a viable approach for type-directed inference of unique solutions for implicit arguments. Performance is comparable to the approach used in Agda, the amount of changes to the Agda implementation is limited, and some long-standing bugs in Agda are fixed.

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